

Tertiary Institution Lecturers' E-Learning Literacy and Competency in North Central Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The digital era has brought about changes in instructional delivery which require lecturers' to develop their e-learning literacy and competency to remain efficient in content delivery. This study investigates e-learning literacy and competency of tertiary institution lecturers in North Central Nigeria. Cross sectional survey design was used for this study. The population of the study comprised of all the tertiary institution lecturers in the region. The respondents of the study were 548 lecturers. A structured questionnaire with two sub scale was used for data collection. The questionnaire was developed by the researchers, validated by three experts and the internal consistency of 0.714 and 0.937 were established using Cronbach Alpha. The responses were analyzed using the descriptive statistics and independent sample t-test. The lecturers were found to have medium level of e-learning literacy and competency. A significant difference was found between male and female lecturers on their e-learning competency and between lecturers of the private and public institutions. However, no significant difference was found between male and female lecturers on their e-learning literacy and between lecturers of the private and public institutions. Based on these findings, it was recommended that training programs such as workshop and seminars focusing on the use of e-learning technologies can be conducted to enhance the lecturer literacy and competency as well as peer mentorship can be encourage to reduce gender and school type disparity among lecturers in the region.

Keywords: e-learning technologies, e-learning literacy, e-learning competency

Introduction

As e-learning technologies continue to advance, many educational opportunities are open for lecturers to developed their e-learning literacy and competency. some of this e-learning literacy and competency include the ability to use digital tools and platforms, navigating online resources, engaging in virtual communication and collaboration, designing and delivering educational content, assessing student performance, and fostering an interactive and inclusive online learning environment (Ballano et al., 2022; Daniel, 2018). E-learning has become more relevant as it has now incorporated virtual reality and artificial intelligence features to enriched educational opportunities (Ibrahim et al., 2024). However, studies have reported that lecturers with poor IT skills had a problem in preparing and conducting online classes which hindered their effective online teaching (Wills & Van der Berg, 2024; Marek et al., 2021). Additionally, Brown & Green (2021) found that many lecturers were not adequately prepared for the transition to online classes due to lack of training, insufficient technical support, and the challenges of maintaining student engagement in a virtual environment.

Equally, tertiary institutions in Nigeria are incorporating e-learning technologies into teaching activities, it is imperative for lecturers to have the necessary e-learning literacy and competency to effectively utilize these tools to enhance teaching and learning. E-learning literacy and competency enables lecturers to create engaging and interactive online courses, which can improve student learning outcomes and satisfaction (Basilotta-Gomez-Pablos et al., 2022). Additionally, e-learning allows lecturers to adapt to various teaching modalities, such as blended learning and fully online courses which are now essential (Ali, 2020). Moreover, e-learning literacy and competency helps lecturers stay current with technological advancements and pedagogical innovations, ensuring their teaching practices remain significant and effective. This also supports the development of students' digital skills, preparing them for the demands of the modern workforce (Kwiatkowska & Wisniewska-Nogaj, 2022).

Although many studies have been conducted nationally and internationally on the lecturers e-learning literacy and competency (Basilotta-Gomez-Pablos et al., 2022; Kwiatkowska & Wisniewska-Nogaj, 2022; Ali, 2020), not much is known on the lecturers e-learning literacy and competency in North Central Nigeria. It is in view of this that this study investigated the level of e-learning literacy and competency of tertiary institution lecturers in North Central Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated and guided the study.

1. What is the level of lecturers' e-learning literacy in North Central Nigeria?
2. What is the level of lecturers' e-learning competency in North Central Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis

The following null hypotheses were also formulated and tested at 0.05 alpha-level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in e-learning literacy between male and female tertiary institution lecturers in North Central Nigeria
2. There is no significant difference in e-learning competency between male and female tertiary institution lecturers in North Central Nigeria
3. There is no significant difference in e-learning literacy between private and public tertiary institution lecturers in North Central Nigeria
4. There is no significant difference in e-learning literacy between private and public tertiary institution lecturers in North Central Nigeria

Literature Review

The emergence of e-learning technologies have expanded the role of lecturers in the development of educational contexts and activities (Ivwithghweta & Efevberha-Ogodo, 2023). In order to successfully use e-learning technologies, lecturers need to develop their own e-learning literacy, like skills related to the accessibility of information, online involvement, computer skills, search engine skills, and information evaluation (McArthur et al., 2018). E-learning literacy is the knowledge and skill required to facilitate teaching and learning, and other educational activities through technologies (Daniel, 2018; Nguyen & Habok, 2022). Daniel (2018) further described e-learning literacy to include several literacies such as digital literacy and metacognitive literacy. Other scholars look at E-learning literacy as not only about knowledge and skills alone but also include attitude of lecturers to use e-learning (Hong & Jung, 2011; Binkley et al., 2012; Nortvig et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2024). Though, studies have found a strong correlation between the e-learning literacy of lecturer and their uses of e-learning technologies (Kehinde & Folorunsho, 2019; Ogunsanya & Buraimo, 2022).

Studies on lecturers' e-learning literacy is inconclusive. For instance, Ogunbodede et al. (2023), Onu et al. (2022), and Ogunsanya and Buraimo, (2021) on their respective studies found that lecturers have high level of digital literacy. While some studies found lecturers with medium level of digital literacy (Baro et al., 2019; Sánchez-Caballé et al., 2022). Other studies found lecturers to have low literacy on e-learning (like, Bolaji and Ibrahim-Raji, 2023; Adejimola et al., 2022; Moses & Yakubu, 2020; Ogechukwu & Peterdamaian, 2020).

On the other hand, e-learning competency has also been found as one of the key factor that influences the uses of e-learning technologies. It enables lecturers to deliver quality education despite geographical and resource constraints, thus equipping students with necessary digital skills (Guri-Rosenblit, 2010; Yen et al., 2018). Lecturer e-learning competency encompasses extend to which lecturer is able to participate in e-learning activities (Daniel, 2018). E-learning competency cover knowledge, skills, and ability to take advantage of e-learning technologies for the purpose of gathering, processing and presenting information in support of teaching activities among different groups of peoples (UNESCO, 2021). Furthermore, e-learning competency is regards to the use of technology to perform tasks, solve problems, communicate, manage information, collaborate, as well as to create and share content effectively (Osuji & Arannilewa, 2022; Redcker, 2017; Skov, 2016).

In this digital age, lecturers often needed to use digital technology to carry out teaching activities. studies have found lecturers with high level of e-learning competency in using different tools of e-learning technologies (Ivwithghweta, 2023; Adenekan, 2023; Kehinde and Folorunsho, 2019). While, few studies revealed the moderate level of lecturer e-learning competency (Maphalala & Adigun, 2020; Rahman et al., 2024). Other studies found lecturers to had low level of e-learning competency (Abdulrazak et al., 2023; Adejimola et al., 2022; Ogechukwu & Peterdamaian, 2020).

Another issues related to effective utilization of e-learning is the gender disparity. Studies have showed difference between male and female lecturer level of e-learning literacy and competency favoring male lecturers (Irfan et al., 2014; Timothy, 2021; Ogunbodede et al., 2023), some favoring female lecturers (Adebayo & Abdulhamid, 2019; Oluwatayo & Adedokun, 2020; Nwosu & Ugwoke, 2021), while other studies showed no gender differences on the lecturers' e-learning literacy and competency (Onu et al., 2022; Ogunbodede et al., 2023; Ogechukwu & Peterdamaian, 2020). Therefore, understanding this differences among lecturers on their level of e-learning literacy and competency are necessary to ensures lecturers fully utilize the advantages of e-learning technologies in their teaching practices.

From the assessment of the reviewed literatures, there is limited studies on lecturers' e-learning literacy and competency in tertiary institutions in North Central Nigeria. It is against this background that this study investigated lecturers' e-learning literacy and competency in North Central Nigeria. This study also focused on the gender and school type disparity among the lecturers' e-learning literacy and competency levels.

Methodology

Cross sectional survey design was used in this study to investigate the lecturer level of e-learning literacy and competency in North Central Nigeria. The population of the study comprised of all the lecturers in the region. The respondents of the study consisted of 548 lecturers (243 males and 345 females) obtained from both public and private tertiary institutions. A structured questionnaire with two sub scale was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts. The internal consistency of the two sub scale were established using the Cronbach Alpha to be 0.714 and 0.937 for e-learning literacy and competency respectively. The instrument was distributed across the region and the data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics and independent sample t-test with aids of SPSS version 21. For the interpretation of result, real limits were used. Where a mean score between 1.00-1.49 refers to low literacy or competency, 1.50- 2.49 as medium literacy or competency and 2.50-3.00 as high literacy or competency.

Results

The results of this study were presented in Table 1 to 6.

Table 1: Frequency, Percentage, Mean and Standard Deviation Responses of Tertiary Institution lecturers' Level of E-learning Literacy

S/N	Items	I don't know this tool	I know this tool	I have the knowledge on how to use this tool	Mean	SD
1	Computer	1(0.1%)	547(99.8%)	540(98.5%)	1.65	0.12
2	Smart phones	2(0.3%)	546(99.6%)	545(99.5%)	1.66	0.08
3	Learning Management System like Moodle, Google Classroom, TutorNG, Canvas, etc.	1(0.1%)	547(99.8%)	541(98.7%)	1.65	0.11
4	Zoom	2(0.3%)	546(99.6%)	540(98.5%)	1.65	0.13
5	Google Tools (e.g. Google Meet, Form, and Sheet etc.)	4(0.7%)	544(99.2%)	537(97.9%)	1.64	0.16
6	Microsoft Team	3(0.5%)	545(99.4%)	538(98.1%)	1.64	0.14
7	E-library	2(0.3%)	546(99.6%)	537(97.9%)	1.64	0.15
8	Educational games	6(1.0%)	542(98.9%)	542(98.9%)	1.65	0.13
9	Open Educational Resources like Simulations, course modules, etc.	8(1.4%)	540(98.5%)	539(98.3%)	1.64	0.16
10	Blended Learning like flipped classroom, gamification, collaborative learning, etc.	5(0.9%)	543(99.0%)	538(98.1%)	1.64	0.15
11	Search engines like google or Ask Mama	2(0.3%)	546(99.6%)	542(98.9%)	1.65	0.11
12	Microsoft Word Application	1(0.1%)	547(99.8%)	543(99.0%)	1.65	0.10
13	Microsoft PowerPoint	2(0.3%)	546(99.6%)	542(98.9%)	1.65	0.11
14	Microsoft Excel	0(0.0%)	548(100.0%)	542(98.9%)	1.65	0.10
15	Electronic whiteboard	21(3.8%)	527(96.1%)	483(88.1%)	1.53	0.36
16	Cloud storage services (Drop box, Google Drive, I Cloud, etc.).	7(1.2%)	541(98.7%)	536(97.8%)	1.64	0.17
17	Social Media like WhatsApp, YouTube	0(0.0%)	548(100.0%)	543(99.0%)	1.65	0.09
18	Online Database	7(1.2%)	541(98.7%)	537 (97.9%)	1.64	0.17
19	School E-mail	2(0.3%)	546(99.6%)	539(98.3%)	1.65	0.15
20	School Websites	1(0.2%)	547(99.8%)	541(98.7%)	1.65	0.11
21	E-book	1(0.2%)	547(99.8%)	542(98.9%)	1.65	0.11
22	Live Webinars with Q&A chats	70(12.7%)	478(87.2%)	471(85.9%)	1.48	0.45

23	Digital Education Tools like Edmodo, Socrative, TED-Ed, etc.	9(1.6%)	539(98.3%)	533(97.2%)	1.63	0.19
Grand Mean					1.63	0.15

Table 1 presents the lecturers' level of e-learning literacy. The overall grand mean of 1.63 which fall within mean rate of medium literacy was found. This grand mean means lecturers have marginally medium levels of e-learning literacy.

Table 2: Frequency, Percentage, Mean and Standard Deviation Responses of Tertiary Institution Lecturers' Level of E-learning Competency

S/N	Items	I can use this tool for teaching	I have used this tool for teaching	I can fix some problems that may arise when using the tool for teaching	Mean	SD
1	Computer	540(98.5%)	540(98.5%)	540(98.5%)	1.97	0.24
2	Smart phones	537(98.0%)	444(81.0%)	403(73.5%)	1.60	0.68
3	Learning Management System like Moodle, Google Classroom, TutorNG, Canvas, etc.	479(87.4%)	391(71.4%)	312(56.9%)	1.33	0.75
4	Zoom	520(94.5%)	520(94.5%)	497(77.0%)	1.55	0.38
5	Google Tools (e.g. Google Meet, Form, and Sheet etc.)	470(85.8%)	410(74.8%)	398(72.6%)	1.51	0.80
6	Microsoft Team	467(85.2%)	406(74.1%)	405(73.9%)	1.51	0.81
7	E-library	465(84.9%)	410(74.8%)	382(69.7%)	1.47	0.81
8	Educational games	465(84.9%)	388(70.8%)	388(70.8%)	1.46	0.84
9	Open Educational Resources like Simulations, course modules, etc.	465(84.9%)	391(71.4%)	390(71.1%)	1.47	0.83
10	Blended Learning like flipped classroom, gamification, collaborative learning, etc.	467(85.2%)	395(72.1%)	383(69.8%)	1.46	0.79
11	Search engines like google or Ask Mama	504(92.0%)	436(79.6%)	400(72.9%)	1.56	0.69
12	Microsoft Word Application	537(98.0%)	455(83.0%)	437(79.7%)	1.67	0.64
13	Microsoft PowerPoint	536(97.8%)	459(83.8%)	452(82.4%)	1.70	0.63
14	Microsoft Excel	486(88.7%)	436(79.6%)	374(68.2%)	1.50	0.73
15	Electronic whiteboard	470(85.8%)	409(74.6%)	397(72.4%)	1.50	0.76
16	Cloud storage services (Drop box, Google Drive, I Cloud, etc.).	466(85.0%)	420(76.6%)	405(73.9%)	1.53	0.78
17	Social Media like WhatsApp, YouTube	535(97.6%)	459(83.8%)	451(82.2%)	1.70	0.57
18	Online Database	499(91.1%)	425(77.6%)	414(75.5%)	1.32	0.61
19	School E-mail	468(85.4%)	393(71.1%)	389(70.9%)	1.47	0.82
20	School Websites	466(85.0%)	391(71.4%)	383(69.8%)	1.45	0.79
21	E-book	466(85.0%)	395(72.1%)	373(68.0%)	1.44	0.80
22	Live Webinars with Q&A chats	463(84.5%)	378(69.0%)	368(67.1%)	1.41	0.79
23	Digital Education Tools like Edmodo, Socrative, TED-Ed, etc.	474(86.5%)	362(66.4%)	347(62.2%)	1.36	0.85

Grand Mean	1.52	0.71
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The results from Table 2 presented the e-learning competency of the lecturers. The grand mean of 1.52 was found which shows lecturers have a marginally medium level of e-learning competency.

Table 3: Independent Sample T-test of Male and Female Tertiary Institution Lecturers' level of E-learning Literacy

Gender	N	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Deviation	t-value	Df	p-value
Male	203	1.62	0.15	-0.19	546	0.84
Female	345	1.63	0.07			

Table 3 shows the result of independent sample t-test analysis of male and female tertiary institution lecturers' level of e-learning literacy in North Central Nigeria. The table revealed no statistical significant difference between male and female lecturers on their level of e-learning literacy in North Central Nigeria with p-value of 0.84.

Table 4: Independent Sample T-test of Male and Female Tertiary Institution Lecturers' level of E-learning Competency

Gender	N	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Deviation	t-value	Df	p-value
Male	203	1.67	0.42	4.56	546	0.00
Female	345	1.43	0.64			

Table 4 shows the result of independent sample t-test analysis of male and female tertiary institution lecturers' level of e-learning competency in North Central Nigeria. The Table shown that there is significant difference between male and female lecturers on their level of e-learning competency with p-value of 0.00.

Table 5: Independent Sample T-test of Private and Public Tertiary Institution Lecturers level of E-learning Literacy

Gender	N	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Deviation	t-value	Df	p-value
Private	84	1.65	0.30	1.49	546	0.13
Public	464	1.63	0.24			

Table 5 indicates the t-value of 1.49 and a p-value of 0.13. This shows that there is no significant difference between lecturers of the private and public tertiary institutions on their e-learning literacy in North Central Nigeria.

Table 6: Independent Sample T-test of between Private and Public Tertiary Institution Lecturers level of E-learning Competency

Gender	N	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Deviation	t-value	Df	p-value
Private	84	1.85	0.16	5.85	546	0.00
Public	464	1.46	0.61			

Table 6 indicates the t-value of 5.85 and a p-value of 0.00. This shows that there is a significant difference between lecturers of the private and public tertiary institutions on their e-learning competency in North Central Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

From table 1, the finding on e-learning literacy among lecturers in North Central Nigeria revealed that lecturers had marginally medium level of e-learning literacy. This implies that lecturers' medium literacy was very closed to low. Though, it was notable from the Table that lecturers had low literacy only on Live Webinar with Q & A chats. While more than 97% had medium literacy in the remaining items. This indicates that lecturers have low knowledge and skills to operate live webinar. The finding on the medium level of lecturers' e-learning literacy conforms to Sánchez-Caballé et al. (2022) and Baro et al. (2019) whose studies found that lecturers' degree of digital proficiency is intermediate. In contrast to the finding of this study, Ogunsanya and Buraimo (2020) investigated the ICT literacy skills among lecturers in Olabisi Onabanjo University (OOU), Nigeria and found that lecturers at OOU exhibited a high level of ICT literacy. Similar finding was found by Ndagi and Madu (2018) among universities lecturers in North Central Nigeria, and Onu et al. (2022) at Colleges of Education in Northwest, Nigeria. This seems to depend on the institutions.

The finding in Table 2 is the result of e-learning competency. It showed that tertiary institution lecturers in North Central Nigeria have medium level of e-learning competency. Similar to that of literacy, the medium competency level of lecturers is very close to low. The finding of this study was in line with Mfon (2016), who found that tertiary institution lecturers in Calabar, Nigeria had medium level of digital proficiency when using social networking sites. However, a study conducted in South-South geopolitical zone, Nigeria by Ogunbodede et al. (2023) found that lecturers possessed very high levels of fundamental digital competence skills and high levels of digital competence in the region. Another study conducted by Adenekan et al. (2023) in South-West Nigeria showed that 79% of the respondents had a high level of technology competence towards the use of E-learning system and 21% had a moderate level towards E-learning. Similar findings were found by Ivwighrehweta (2023) among lecturers in Michael and Cecilia Ibru University, Esteve-Mon et al. (2020) among lecturers from two European universities, Oyedokun (2018) in some selected universities in Kwara State, and Noskova et al. (2021) on Russian universities lecturers.

The finding in Table 3 revealed no significant difference was found on the e-learning literacy between male and female lecturers. In other words, this finding attest to the fact that lecturer e-learning literacy did not vary by gender. This is in consistent with the findings of Onu et al. (2022), Yarkofoji (2021), and Macqual and Ichakpa (2014) who respectively found no significant difference between male and female lecturers e-learning literacy. In contrast, Timothy, (2021) and Idika et al. (2024) respectively found significant difference between male and female lecturers' e-learning literacy.

The finding in Table 4 showed significant difference emerged between male and female lecturers on their level of e-learning competency. This implies that lecturers level of e-learning competency vary according to gender. According to Nwamaka et al. (2023) and Udoudo et al. (2021), who interpreted the differences could be as a result of male lecturers are more curious in applying their skills in using e-learning technologies than their female counterparts which might be the same with this finding. The finding that male lecturers are more competency in using e-learning technologies agrees with Emelogu et al. (2022) which found that male lecturers are more proficient than female lecturers in the use of ICTs for teaching. However, disagrees with Owan et al. (2021) who revealed female lecturers had higher rate of preparedness for the use of ICTs during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The finding in Table 5 indicate no significant difference was found on the e-learning literacy between lecturers of the private and public institutions. This implies that the medium e-learning literacy levels of lecturers did not vary according to school type. This is in consistent with previous studies that found no significant difference between the lecturers of private and public institutions on e-learning literacy (Lucero et al., 2021; Okeke & Nwosu, 2021; Hilton et al., 2020). Unlike, studies that found significant difference between the lecturers of the private and public institutions (Soyemi, 2018; Kuliya & Usman, 2020).

The finding in Table 6 indicate a significant difference between the lecturers of the private and public institutions. This is consistent with the findings of Gutierrez-Angel et al. (2022), Heriyanto et al. (2022) and Ballano et al. (2022) who found in their respective studies that lecturers competency in using e-learning technologies vary between the private and public institutions. Contrary to this study, other studies found no significant differences between the lecturers of private and public institutions on their e-learning competency (Adebayo & Balogun, 2019; Nwankwo, & Okeke, 2020).

Conclusion and Recommendations

E-learning literacy and competency are essential for lecturers in this digital age. However, it is of concern to note that lecturers in North Central Nigeria are having marginal medium level of e-learning literacy and competency. Therefore, this study recommends organization of workshop and seminars to improve the lecturers' e-learning literacy and competency for effective utilization of e-learning technologies in the region.

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